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Organisational Purpose as Correlate of Business Survival in Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

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ABSTRACT

This study examined organisational purpose as a correlate of business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The study was guided by two research questions and two research hypotheses. The study adopted a cross-sectional correlational survey design with a population of 220 approved private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. A sample size of 140 was drawn using Krejcie & Morgan Table on sample size determination. 140 copies of questionnaires were administered to respondents out of which 107 representing 76% were found valid for the analysis. All items on the questionnaire had a Cronback Alpha threshold of 0.7 and above in the reliability test. The research questions were answered and the hypotheses tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation statistics and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences. The result of the data analysed revealed that there is a high and positive relationship between mission and vision statements and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. Based on the findings it was recommended that proprietors of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State should develop a clear mission statement to provide a sense of direction towards the attainment of business goals. Proprietors of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State should develop a vision statement that clearly define a desired future state.

Keywords: Business Survival, Mission, Purpose, Vision

INTRODUCTION

In today's fast-paced and competitive market landscape, the survival of businesses hinge on its ability to achieve success. Success implies the attainment of fundamental objectives, which in turn generate revenue essential for economic well-being (Lynch, 2019). The ever-changing business environment, characterized by intense market competition, rapid technological advancements, and shifting socio-economic ideologies, has increased market volatility and uncertainty. This heightened pressure to survive has led to a staggering 80% of businesses failing within the first five years (Bryant, 2022).

Given the dynamic nature of the business environment, it is imperative that businesses identify and engage suitable strategies to effectively compete and navigate the various barriers that characterize their context. According to Montgomery (2012), understanding the purpose of a business is crucial for its survival and success, as it defines why the firm exists and what unmet needs it intends to fill. Organisational purpose is a vital component of an organisation's overall strategy and identity (Bart,

2007). It provides a sense of direction, motivation, and meaning for stakeholders, including employees, customers, and investors (Collins & Porras, 1996). Henderson & Van den Steen (2015) defined purpose as a concrete goal or objective that reaches beyond profit maximization. The authors further posited that mission and vision statements are two fundamental dimensions of organizational purpose. In the context of schools, organisational purpose is often reflected in mission and vision statements, which serve as guiding principles for decision making and resource allocation (Kotter, 1995). Research has shown that organisational purpose is positively related to organisational performance (Bart, 2007; Collings & Porras, 1996). In the education sector studies have found that schools with a clear sense of purpose tend to perform better academically and have higher levels of student satisfaction (Leithwood & Jantzi, 2005; Mulford, 2003).

Strategic plans are primarily created to support the mission, which is a crucial and essential document for forming organisations and providing clear guidelines for decision making. The mission is a crucial component and foundation upon which the school relies to establish its vision and objectives. This is a concise overview of the process of briefly elucidating the purpose of its existence, or in other terms, stating what its goal is (Monye, 2019). The school's mission statement outlines its overarching objectives. Additionally, it serves as a mechanism that drives and motivates personnel, students, parents, capturing their interest and dedication toward the objectives of the school. A school's mission statement acts as a guide to educators, students, families and the community of what the school values, believes, does and aspires to be. A strong vision based on collective values provides the foundation for staff commitment, student success, and sustained school growth (Huffman, 2001).

A vision can be described as an ambitious and future-oriented statement of what an individual or schools achieves. It encompasses a medium to long term time frame, typically referring to the distant future (Baidon & Arabi, 2023). The main purpose of articulating a vision is to use it as a guiding principle in determining the school's actions, policies, and events both now and in the future. It is also a program that is oriented toward the future, and it can be stated that the school's vision is what shapes the desired future state it aims for (Jonyo, Ouma & Mosoti (2018). Businesses that do not rely on the presence of a clear vision will not achieve enduring success (Khivya, Jeeva, Devi, Suguna & Shanthini, 2019). The vision facilitates the attainment of an institution or company's objectives by engaging all its members in their accomplishments. The vision further helps personnel attain their goals and achieving the enduring essence of their work (Othman, 2022).

Jonyo, Ouma & Mosoti (2018) carried out a study on the effect of Mission and Vision on organisational performance within private universities in Kenya. The study concluded that there was a significant relationship between vision and mission and organisational performance. Utaya & Wafaretta (2021) examined the influence of vision, mission and performance of environmental education at Adiwiyata Elementary School in Malang City, Indonesia. Findings revealed a strong positive link between vision, mission and the achievement of outstanding academic performance in the school. In a study on the influence of vision and mission related to accreditation in improving the quality of school education, Pardilla (2024) concluded that the impact of vision and mission has a strong influence on accreditation in improving the quality of school education. Related studies have demonstrated the significance of mission statements in influencing organizational performance. A study by (Sofijanovna & Marianovna, 2014) found a positive correlation between comprehensive mission statements and market share in the confectionery industry in Macedonia. Baum *et al.* (1998), found that the content and attributes of vision statements can impact a company's growth, although factors such as context, size, and setting can influence their effectiveness.

A few earlier studies, however, concluded that there was no evidence to support the idea that mission statements are positively related to company performance. For instance, Bart and Baetz (1998) found no empirical evidence to support the concept that outstanding organizational performance is related to a firm's mission statement even though they concluded that some specific characteristics of a mission statement may be selectively related to higher levels of performance.

Overall, the literature suggests that both mission and vision statements play a crucial role in influencing business survival. Because the results of these previous studies are conflicting, it is necessary to further investigate the link between mission, vision and business survival. This study, as a departure from previous studies, thus addresses the relationship between organisational purpose as a correlate of business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the critical role of private secondary schools in Nigeria's education sector, many of these institutions face significant challenges that impact their overall survival. One often overlooked factor that may contribute to these challenges is the lack of a clear and compelling organisational purpose. Research has shown that a strong sense of purpose can have a positive impact on organisational performance, employee engagement and overall survival. However, there is a dearth of research on the relationship between organisational purpose and business survival in the context of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. This study aims to address this knowledge gap by investigating the correlate between organisational purpose and business survival of private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine organisational purpose as a correlate of business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study were to:

- i. Ascertain the relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State
- ii. Ascertain the relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?
2. What is the relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted a correlational survey design with a population of 220 private secondary schools approved by the Rivers State Ministry of Education operational in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. In advancing the sample size for this research, the Krejcie and Morgan 1970 sample size determination table was adopted. A sample size of 140 was determined and adopted for this research. The probability sampling technique was adopted using the simple random sampling method. To facilitate data collection, the Proprietors of 140 private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State were selected purposively as they were deemed to have the adequate knowledge on the purpose of their schools. The instruments for data collection were researcher-designed questionnaires titled "Organisational Purpose as Correlate of Business Survival of Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State". The instrument comprises two sections: Section A and Section B. Section A was designed to collect the biodata of respondents while Section B comprises items aimed at providing relevant information in respect to the research questions. Questionnaire items were designed on a five-point Likert scale of strongly Agree (SA)=5, Agree (A)=4, Neutral (N)=3, Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. The

instrument validity by two experts. The internal consistencies of the instruments were determined using the Cronbach Alpha method which yielded a reliability index of 0.872, which showed that the instruments were reliable. Out of the 140 copies of the questionnaire administered, 107 were retrieved and used for analysis. The researcher questions were answered based on the value and direction of the correlation coefficient (positive and high, positive but low, or negative and high or negative but low or moderate. Values of 0.1-0.4 were counted as low correlation, values of 0.5 were considered moderate correlation while 0.6-1.0 were considered high correlation. Similarly, the hypotheses were tested for significance of relationship at 0.05 level of significance.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *What is the relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?*

Table 1: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Mission Statement and Business Survival in Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State

Correlations

		MISSION	BUSSURV
MISSION	Pearson Correlation	1	.973**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
BUSSURV	Pearson Correlation	.973**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data 2025

The analysis from Table 1 revealed a correlation value of $r=0.931$. This value is high and positive, thus indicating that there is a high and positive relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The result suggest that mission statement influences business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Research Question 2: *What is the relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State?*

Table 2: Pearson Product Moment Correlation on Relationship between Vision Statement and Business Survival in Private Secondary Schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Correlations

		VISION	BUSSURV
VISION	Pearson Correlation	1	.587**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	107	107
BUSSURV	Pearson Correlation	.587**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	107	107

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Research Data 2025

The analysis from Table 2 revealed a correlation value of $r = 0.587$. This value is moderately high and positive, thus indicating that there is a positive relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. This result implied that the

adoption of vision statement influences business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Test of Hypotheses

Table 1 illustrates the result on the test on the relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. Results from the analysis show that mission statement significantly impacts business survival ($r = 0.931$ and $P = 0.000$). The evidence from the analysis thus demonstrates the significance of mission statement in predicting business survival. The related null hypothetical statement earlier postulated is rejected as the result shows as follows:

H₁: There is a significant relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

Table 2 illustrates the result on the test on the relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. Results from the analysis show that mission statement significantly impacts business survival ($r = 0.587$ and $P = 0.000$). The evidence from the analysis thus demonstrates the significance of vision statement in predicting business survival. The related null hypothetical statement earlier postulated is rejected as the result shows as follows:

H₂: There is a significant relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The result of the findings of the study for research question 1 on Table 1 revealed that respondents believed there is a high and positive relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The study revealed that mission statement increases the chances of business survival by providing a sense of direction and purpose, serves as a key driver in decision making processes, clearly defining purpose and goals, providing inspiration, aligning values and goals through regular review and update lead to business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The corresponding hypothesis one revealed that there is a significant relationship between mission statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. This is in line with the findings of Sojijanova & Marjanova (2014), who conducted research on Corporate Mission Statement and Business Performance: Through the Prism of Macedonian Companies and concluded that there is a positive relationship between Mission statement and Business performance. Corroborating this view, Jonyo, Ouma & Mosoti (2018) who carried out a study on the effect of Mission and Vision on organisational performance within private universities in Kenya concluded that there was a significant relationship between vision and mission and organisational performance. Therefore, having a mission statement is an effective way to increase the chances of business survival.

The result of the finding of the study for research question two on Table 2 revealed that respondents believed there is a moderately high and positive relationship between having a vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. It was revealed that vision statement clearly defines desired future state and provides inspiration, as well as a sense of direction and purpose. The corresponding hypotheses two revealed that there is a significant relationship between vision statement and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. The findings of this study agrees with Pardilla (2024) whose study on the influence of vision and mission related to accreditation in improving the quality of school education revealed and strong relationship between the variables. This was in line with earlier findings by Baum *et al*, (1998) who conducted a longitudinal study of the Relationship of Vision and Vision Communication to Venture Growth in Entrepreneurial Firms. The author concluded that the content and attributes of vision statements can impact a company's growth, although factors such as context, size, and setting can influence their effectiveness

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study it was concluded that there was a significant positive relationship between organisational purpose and business survival in private secondary schools in Port Harcourt Urban, Rivers State. In other words, the adoption of these statements by management of private secondary schools would lead to the survival of these schools.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Proprietors of private secondary schools should develop clear mission statements to provide a sense of direction, which will inspire teachers, students and other stakeholders.
2. Proprietors of private secondary schools should develop vision statements that clearly defined desired future state, which will inspire teachers, students and other stakeholders.

REFERENCES

- Bart, C.K. (2007). A comparative analysis of mission statement content in secular and faith-based hospitals. *Journal of Healthcare Management*, 52 (4), 265-278.
- Bryant, S. (2022). How many startups fail and why? Retrieved from <https://www.investopedia.com/articles/personal-finance/040915/how-many-startups-failand-why.asp>
- Baildon, M.C. & Arbai, H.M (2023). Time to Re-Envision Vision Statements in Education. In restricting Leadership for School Improvement and Reform. IGI Global.
- Bart, C. & M. Baetz. (1998). The relationship between mission statements and firm performance: An exploratory study. *Journal of Management Studies*, 35: 823-826.
- Baum, J. R., Locke, E. A., & Kirkpatrick, S. A. (1998). A Longitudinal Study of the Relation of Vision and Vision Communication to Venture Growth in Entrepreneurial Firms. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 83(1), 43-54.
- Collins, J.C., & Porras, J.I. (1996). Building your company's vision. *Harvard Business Review*, 74(5).
- Henderson, R., & Van den Steen, E. (2015). Why do firms have purpose? *Harvard Business Review*, 93(6), 123-126
- Huffman, Jane. *The Role of Shared Values and Vision in Creating Professional Learning Communities*. Southwest Educational Development Lab., Austin, TX. Office of Educational Research and Improvement (ED), Washington, DC. 2001-00-00
- Jonyo, B.O., Ouma, C., & Mosoti Z. (2018). The effect of Mission and Vision on Organisational Performance within Private Universities in Kenya. *European Journal of Educational Sciences* (5(2)
- Khivya, M., Jeeva, N., Devi, KG, Suguna, S.K & Shanthini, S. (2019). Impact of Vision, Mission and program educational objectives for augmenting the quality of education in academic institutions. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*. 9(5).
- Kotter, J.P. (1995). Leading change: why transformation efforts fail. *Harvard Business Review*, 73(2).
- Leithwood, K., & Jantzi, D. (2005). Transformational leadership. In J.C. Collins & D.C. Hambrick (Eds.), *The Oxford handbook of leadership*. Oxford University Press
- Lynch, R. (2019). Towards an innovation link between dynamic capabilities and sustainability strategy: options for emerging market companies. *International Journal of Innovation and Technology Management*, 16 (04), 194003
- Montgomery, C. A. (2012). *The Strategist: Be the leader your business needs*. HarperCollins Publishers, New York
- Mulford, W.R. (2003). School leaders: Changing leadership practice in changing times. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 31(1)
- Moye, J.N (2019). Creating Shared Mission, Vision and Values. In a Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence Approach to Institutional Effectiveness in Higher Education. Emerald Publishing Limited.

- Othman, N (2022). The relationship of vision and mission to the mental image of the Library and Information programme at the Faculty of Arts, Menoufia University. A case study of an accredited program. *International Journal of Library and Information Sciences* 9(1)
- Pardilla, P. (2024). The influence of Vision and Mission related to Accreditation in Improving the Quality of School Education. *SIJE-Student International Journal of Education*, I(1).
- Sofijanova, E., Marjanova, T. J. (2014). Corporate Mission Statement and Business Performance: Through the Prism of Macedonian Companies. *Balkan Social Science Review*, 3, 179-198.
- Utaya, S., & Wafaretta, V. (2021). The vision, mission and implementation of environmental education of Adiwiyata elementary school in Malang City. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science*, 802(1), IOP Publishing.